

A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Benfontein Nature Reserve in the Northern Cape province, South Africa

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ABSTRACT: The aim of this study was to compile the first checklist of the spider species in the Northern Cape province at the Benfontein Nature Reserve. Spiders were collected during different survey periods using different collecting methods to sample both the ground and field layers. In total, 36 families represented by 112 genera and 167 species have been collected so far. The most species-rich families are the Gnaphosidae (35 spp.) and Salticidae (21 spp.), followed by the Lycosidae (11 spp.) and Araneidae (11 spp.), while 10 families are represented by singletons. Information on endemism value and conservation status are provided. Most of the species (92.2%) in the Benfontein Nature Reserve have a wide distribution with no known threats, with eight species that are data deficient and five were not evaluated. A large number of species (40.7%) are known throughout Southern Africa, while 21.6% of the species found in the reserve are African endemics, 49 spp. (29.3%) are South African endemics, and only four species (2.4%) are Northern Cape endemics.

Keywords: biodiversity, conservation, red list, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

The South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) collates species distribution data that are essential information needed for the conservation assessments when compiling a Red Data List (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015; Foord *et al.*, 2020). Survey data are needed to obtain species-specific information, and to determine new, rare, and/or endemic species and resources that are already in place in existing protected areas. The publication of these species checklists formed the basis of the first spider atlas (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010). The data are also used by the different provinces in their biodiversity assessments and action plans.

In South Africa, although the Northern Cape is the largest province (29.7%), it is still one of the poorest-sampled provinces, with only 490 spp. represented by 49 families known (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). Several surveys have been conducted in the province but only a few checklists have been published such as spider diversity in pistachio orchards in the arid Northern Cape at Prieska (Haddad *et al.*, 2004, 2005, 2008; Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2005); spiders from the Tswalu Kalahari Game Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2018), and the Augrabies National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021).

The current study presents the results of SANSA sampling and by-catch sampling in the Benfontein Nature Reserve on the border of the Northern Cape and Free State. Benfontein Nature Reserve (BNR) forms part of the Diamond Route Reserves, a set of sites across South Africa that conserve biodiversity and provide education and sustainability opportunities through the De Beers Group of Companies, E. Oppenheimer and Son and Ponahalo Investments. It is currently being managed as a nature reserve. Information on spider guilds, their habitat preference, and endemism index and conservation status are provided.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study area: BNR (-28.841, 24.851) is situated 14 km south-east of Kimberley and consists of flat plains on the central South African plateau at an altitude of about 1 180 m.a.s.l. with an area covering 11 000 ha (Figs 1 & 2).

It consists of a large calcrete pan (300 ha in size and c. 6 km in length) in the north-west that fills with water during good rains, creating a fertile shallow wetland. Specialised salt-tolerant plant communities surround the pan and two prominent drainage lines flow into it from the east. Away from the pan, the ground levels off and red Kalahari sand occurs to the south-east.

BNR is located in a transitional zone where Karoo, grassland and Kalahari thornveld savannah meet. The vegetation is mostly semi-open savanna of the Savanna Biome, with the Nama Karoo Biome present around the pan. There are three vegetation types: Highveld Salt Pans, Northern Upper Karoo, and Kimberley Thornveld. In the Kimberley Thornveld, the vegetation is generally open camel thorn *Vachellia erioloba* savanna in tall grass on deep red sands. The grass layer is complex and is dominated by *Eragrostis* species, silky grasses *Stipagrostis* species and stick grasses *Aristida* species. After good rains the flat country in the east becomes grassy, with red grass *Themeda triandra* and turpentine grass *Cymbopogon plurinodis* dominating.

Figure 1. Benfontein Nature Reserve

FIGURE 2: Map showing the location of the locality of the Benfontein Nature Reserve in the Northern Cape province.

Sampling method and period: Different surveys were undertaken over several years (1981–2018) (Table 1). The main focus was ground fauna sampling using pitfall traps. Identification was done by both authors. All the sampled material were deposited as voucher specimens at the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) of the Agricultural Research Council in Pretoria. Only the generic names were included in the checklist when immature specimens were sampled and where some families lack taxonomic research to make species level identifications impossible.

TABLE 1: Surveys undertaken at the Benfontein Nature Reserve.

SURVEY TEAM	SAMPLING PROTOCOL	DATE
S. Erasmus (student)	Pitfall traps by-catch termite survey (by-catch)	1981 (12 months)
F. Dalerum	Pitfall traps sampling (by-catch)	2006–2011
C. Haddad	ad hoc sampling	2010
H. Badenhorst (student)	Pitfall traps sampling	2018

Endemicity value: The global distribution of species was used to determine the endemicity value of each species (Table 3).

Values used to indicate species endemicity (E):

- 6 – only known from the type locality (BNR);
- 5 – known from several localities in the Northern Cape (NCE);
- 4 – known from Northern Cape as well as a adjacent provinces;
- 3 – known from more than two provinces in South Africa (SAE);
- 2 – known from other Southern African countries (STHE);
- 1 – known from other countries in the Afrotropical Region (AE)
- 0 – also from countries outside the Afrotropical Region (CE).

Conservation status: The conservation status of each species was derived from a recent National Red List assessment of spiders in South Africa (Foord *et al.*, 2020) where spatial analysis on observed occurrences using functions for Extent of Occurrence (EOO), Area of Occupancy (AOO), and elevational range the area of occupation was determined. The assumed knowledge of the full range for all species based on their observed occurrences, and EOO was calculated as the minimum convex polygon around all occurrences, and the 2 km² cells occupied were used to calculate AOO.

The distribution of threats across lineages was visualized using a mosaic plot, with the size of rectangles representing the proportion of species in a specific family represented within four categories: data deficient (DD), least concern (LC), rare, and threatened (Foord *et al.*, 2020).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numbers present: A total of 167 species in 112 genera and 36 families were recorded (Tables 2 & 4). With the high number of pitfall traps used, the family Gnaphosidae was the most diverse family, with 35 species sampled, followed by the Salticidae with 21 species, and Araneidae and Lycosidae (11 spp.) (Table 2). Ten of the families are known only from a single species.

It compares well with the diversity of Tswalu Kalahari Reserve where 32 families represented by 108 genera and 136 species have been collected so far (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2018).

TABLE 2: The spider families, genera (GEN) and species (SPP.) sampled at the Benfontein Nature Reserve in the Northern Cape, South Africa.

FAMILY	GEN	SPP.	FAMILY	GEN	SPP.
Agelenidae	3	4	Oxyopidae	2	3
Araneidae	8	11	Palpimanidae	2	2
Caponiidae	1	1	Philodromidae	5	5
Cheiracanthiidae	1	2	Pholcidae	2	4
Corinnidae	3	3	Phyxelididae	1	1
Ctenidae	1	1	Pisauridae	2	2
Cyrtacheniidae	1	4	Prodidomidae	2	3
Dictynidae	1	1	Salticidae	10	21
Eresidae	3	4	Scytodidae	1	2
Gallieniellidae	1	1	Segestriidae	1	1
Gnaphosidae	14	35	Sicariidae	2	2
Hersiliidae	1	1	Sparassidae	2	2
Idiopidae	2	2	Theraphosidae	1	1
Linyphiidae	2	2	Theridiidae	5	7
Lycosidae	8	11	Thomisidae	8	9
Oecobiidae	1	1	Trachelidae	4	4
Oonopidae	4	5	Zodariidae	5	7
Orsolobidae	1	1	36	112	167

Conservation status: Most of the species 154 (92.2%) have a wide distribution range and are listed as Least Concern while eight species are Data Deficient, lacking distribution or taxonomic resolution (Table 3). Species of the three genera (*Castianeira*, *Dictyna*, and *Orchestina*) still lack taxonomic resolution and five were not evaluated. The Orsolobidae species sampled is possibly new to science (Table 4).

Species endemicity: A large percentage of species (36 spp., 21.6%) have a wide distribution throughout Africa, while 9 spp. (5.3%) are also found wider than Africa. A total of 68 spp. (40.7%) are endemics to Southern Africa and 49 spp. (29.3%) are South African endemics.

The following four species are endemic to the Northern Cape (Table 4): *Ancylotrypa namaquensis* Purcell, 1908), *A. pusilla* (Purcell, 1903) (Cyrtacheniidae), *Cydrela friedlanderae* Hewitt, 1914, and *Cyrioceta lotzi* Jocqué, 2013 (Zodariidae), while *Opopaea gaborone* Saaristo & Marusik, 2008 (Oonopidae) is for the first time reported from South Africa. BNR is the type locality of *Austrachelas kalaharinus* Haddad, Lyle, Bosselaers & Ramirez, 2009.

TABLE 3: Conservation status and endemism of the spider species sampled at Benfontein Nature Reserve.

CONSERVATION STATUS	SPP.	CODE	%
Data deficient (taxonomic reason or lack distribution data)	8	DD	4.8
Not evaluated (immature, new or undetermined)	5	NE	2.9
Least concern	154	LC	92.2
ENDEMICITY			
0 – Africa and wider (C)	9	LC	5.3
1 – African endemics (AE)	36	LC	21.6
2 – Southern African endemics (STHE)	68	LC	40.7
3 – South African endemics (SAE): More than three provinces	31	LC	18.6
4 – South African endemics (SAE): Two adjacent provinces	14	DD/LC	8.3
5 – Northern Cape endemics (NCE)	4	DD/LC	2.4
6 – Known only from type locality	0		0

CONCLUSION

This survey forms part of the SANSa survey for the Northern Cape province and, as such, represents new distribution records for 167 species. Although this paper probably represents only a portion of the spider fauna present, we hope this information will stimulate further interest and research. Established reserves, such as BNR, can make a substantial contribution towards invertebrate conservation. However, the contribution of existing reserves can only be highlighted through studies such as this.

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Figures 3–17. Spiders from Benfontein Nature Reserve. **Caponiidae**: 3. *Caponia capensis*. **Cyrtachenidae**: 4. *Ancylotrypa pusilla*. 5. *Ancylotrypa pretoriae*. **Eresidae**: 6. *Seothyra fasciata*. **Araneidae**: 7. *Kilima decens*. **Eresidae**: 8. *Gandanameno spenceri*. **Gnaphosidae**: 9. *Ammoxenus coccineus*. 10. *Asemesthes oconnori*. 11. *Drassodes lophognathus*. 12. *Nomisia varia*. **Hersiliidae**: 13. *Tyrotama australis*. **Lycosidae**: 14. *Evippomma squamulatum*. 15. *Hogna schreineri*. **Philodromidae**: 16. *Hirriusa arenacea*. **Palpimanidae**: 17. *Diaphorocellus biplagiatus*. Photos: Peter Webb.

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Figures 18–32. Spiders from Benfontein Nature Reserve. **Salticidae**: 18. *Baryphas ahenus*. 19. *Heliophanus pistaciae*. 20. *Natta chionogaster*. 21. *Pellenes bulawayoensis*. **Pisauridae**: 22. *Rothus aethiopicus*. **Prodidomidae**: 23. *Theuma foveolate*. **Sicariidae**: 24. *Hexophthalma hahni*. **Sparassidae**: 25. *Arandisa deserticola*. 26. *Eusparassus schoemanae*. **Thomisidae**: 27. *Pherecydes tuberculatus*. 28. *Thomisus stenningi*. 29. *Stiphropus affinis*. **Trachelidae**: 30. *Orthobula arca*. **Zodariidae**: 31. *Diores poweri*. 32. *Heradida loricata*. Photos: Peter Webb.

TABLE 4. Checklist of the spiders species recorded from the Benfontein Nature Reserve in the Northern Cape with information on their endemism (END), conservation status (CON), country endemism (CEND) and provincial endemics (PROVE). * possibly new species or new record.

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
AGELENIDAE	<i>Agelena australis</i> Simon, 1896	1	LC	AE
	<i>Agelena gaerdesi</i> Roewer, 1955	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Benoitia deserticola</i> (Simon, 1910)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Mistaria zuluana</i> (Roewer, 1955)	2	LC	STHE
ARANEIDAE	<i>Argiope australis</i> (Walckenaer, 1805)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Caerostris sexcuspidata</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C
	<i>Kilima decens</i> (Blackwall, 1866) (Fig. 7)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Larinia bifida</i> Tullgren, 1910	1	LC	AE
	<i>Larinia natalensis</i> (Grasshoff, 1971)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Nemoscolus cotti</i> Lessert, 1933	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Neoscona blondeli</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Neoscona triangula</i> (Keyserling, 1864)	0	LC	C
	<i>Zygiella x-notata</i> (Clerck, 1757)	0	LC	C
CAPONIIDAE	<i>Caponia capensis</i> Purcell, 1904 (Fig. 3)	2	LC	STHE
CHEIRACANTHIIDAE	<i>Cheiramiona ferrumfontis</i> Lotz, 2002	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Cheiramiona boschrandensis</i> Lotz, 2015	4	DD	SAE
CORINNIDAE	<i>Castianeira</i> sp. (undetermined)		NE	
	<i>Cambalida fulvipes</i> Simon, 1896	1	LC	AE
	<i>Copuetta lotzi</i> Haddad, 2013	3	LC	SAE
CTENIDAE	<i>Ctenus spectabilis</i> Lessert, 1921	1	LC	AE
CYRTAUCHENIIDAE	<i>Ancylotrypa namaquensis</i> (Purcell, 1908)	5	LC	SAE
	<i>Ancylotrypa pusilla</i> (Purcell, 1903) (Fig. 4)	5	LC	SAE
	<i>Ancylotrypa pretoriae</i> (Hewitt, 1913) (Fig. 5)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Ancylotrypa sororum</i> (Hewitt, 1916)	3	LC	SAE
DICTYNIDAE	<i>Dictyna</i> sp.(undetermined)		NE	
ERESIDAE	<i>Gandanameno spenceri</i> (Pocock, 1900) (Fig. 8)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Paradonea parva</i> (Tucker, 1920)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Paradonea splendens</i> (Lawrence, 1936)	3	DD	SAE
	<i>Seothyra fasciata</i> Purcell, 1904 (Fig. 6)	2	LC	STHE
GALLIENIELLIDAE	<i>Austrachelas kalaharinus</i> Haddad, Lyle, Bosselaers & Ramirez, 2009 HT*	4	DD	SAE
GNAPHOSIDAE	<i>Ammoxenus coccineus</i> Simon, 1893 (Fig. 9)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Aneplasa nigra</i> Tucker, 1923	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Asemesthes ceresicola</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Asemesthes lineatus</i> Purcell, 1908	1	LC	AE
	<i>Asemesthes montanus</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Asemesthes oconnori</i> Tucker, 1923 (Fig. 10)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Asemesthes paynteri</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Asemesthes purcelli</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Camillina cordifera</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Camillina maun</i> Platnick & Murphy, 1987	1	LC	AE
	<i>Drassodes ereptor</i> Purcell, 1907	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Drassodes lophognathus</i> Purcell, 1907(Fig. 11)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Drassodes solitarius</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Drassodes splendens</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
	<i>Drassodes stationis</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Echemus erutus</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Ibala bilinearis</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Ibala bulawayensis</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Megamyrmaekion schreineri</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Megamyrmaekion transvaalense</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Micaria beaufortia</i> Tucker, 1923	1	LC	AE
	<i>Nomisia varia</i> (Tucker, 1923) (Fig.12)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Rastellus deserticola</i> Haddad, 2003	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Setaphis browni</i> (Tucker, 1923)	0	LC	C
	<i>Xerophaeus aridus</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Xerophaeus lightfooti</i> Purcell, 1907	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Xerophaeus spoliator</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Xerophaeus spiralifer</i> Purcell, 1907	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Xerophaeus vickermani</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Zelotes corrugatus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Zelotes frenchi</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Zelotes lavus</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Zelotes sclateri</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Zelotes scrutatus</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1872)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Zelotes tuckeri</i> Roewer, 1951	1	LC	AE
HERSILIIDAE	<i>Tyrotama australis</i> (Simon, 1893) (Fig. 13)	2	LC	STHE
IDIOPIDAE	<i>Gorgyrella schreineri</i> Purcell, 1903	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Idiops pullus</i> Tucker, 1917	4	LC	SAE
LINYPHIIDAE	<i>Agyneta habra</i> (Locket, 1968)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Pelecopsis janus</i> Jocqué, 1984	2	LC	STHE
LYCOSIDAE	<i>Allocosa aurichelis</i> Roewer, 1959	4	DD	SAE
	<i>Evippomma squamulatum</i> (Simon, 1898) (Fig. 14)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Hogna schreineri</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Hogna spenceri</i> (Pocock, 1898) (Fig. 15)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Hogna transvaalica</i> (Simon, 1898)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Lycosa rimicola</i> Purcell, 1903	4	DD	SAE
	<i>Pardosa crassipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Pardosa injucunda</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1876)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Proevippa albiventris</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Tricassa deserticola</i> Simon, 1910	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Zenonina mystacina</i> Simon, 1898	2	LC	STHE
OECOBIIDAE	<i>Uroctea quinquenotata</i> Simon, 1910	4	LC	SAE
OONOPIIDAE	<i>Dysderina speculifera</i> Simon, 1907	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Gamasomorpha humicola</i> Lawrence, 1947	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Opopaea speciosa</i> (Lawrence, 1952)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Opopaea gaborone</i> Saaristo & Marusik, 2008	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Orchestina</i> sp. (undetermined)		NE	
ORSOLOBIDAE	<i>Afrilobus</i> possible new sp.		NE	
OXYOPIIDAE	<i>Oxyopes bothai</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes jacksoni</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
	<i>Peucetia viridis</i> (Blackwall, 1858)	1	LC	AE
PALPIMANIDAE	<i>Diaphorocellus biplagiatus</i> Simon, 1893	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Palpimanus namaquensis</i> Simon, 1910 (Fig. 17)	2	LC	STHE

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
Philodromidae	<i>Hirriusa arenacea</i> (Lawrence, 1927) (Fig. 16)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Philodromus browningi</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Suemus punctatus</i> Lawrence, 1938	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Thanatus vulgaris</i> Simon, 1870	0	LC	C
	<i>Tibellus minor</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
Pholcidae	<i>Quamtana</i> sp. immature		NE	
	<i>Smeringopus koppies</i> Huber, 2012	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Smeringopus lotzi</i> Hubert, 2012	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Smeringopus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1947	2	LC	STHE
Phyxelididae	<i>Vidole sothoana</i> Griswold, 1990	2	LC	STHE
Pisauridae	<i>Cispus kimbius</i> Blandin, 1978	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> (Pavesi, 1883) (Fig. 22)	1	LC	AE
Prodidomidae	<i>Austrodomus scaber</i> (Purcell, 1904)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Theuma foveolata</i> Tucker, 1923 (Fig. 23)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Theuma maculata</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
Salticidae	<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902 (Fig. 18)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Evarcha prosimilis</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	1	LC	AE
	<i>Heliophanus charlesi</i> Wesolowska, 2003	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Heliophanus debilis</i> Simon, 1901	1	LC	AE
	<i>Heliophanus nanus</i> Wesolowska, 2003	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Heliophanus pistaciae</i> Wesolowska, 2003 (Fig. 19)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Heliophanus prozyskii</i> Wesolowska, 2003	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Heliophanus termitophagus</i> Wesolowska & Haddad, 2002	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Icius insolitus</i> (Wesolowska, 1999)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Langona warchalowskii</i> Wesolowska, 2007	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Langona hirsuta</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Menemerus transvaalicus</i> Wesolowska, 1999	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Natta chionogaster</i> (Simon, 1901) (Fig. 20)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Pellenes bulawayoensis</i> Wesolowska, 2000 (Fig. 21)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Pellenes geniculatus</i> (Simon, 1868)	0	LC	C
	<i>Pellenes modicus</i> Wesolowska & Russell-Smith, 2000	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Pellenes tharinae</i> Wesolowska, 2007	3	LC	STHE
	<i>Phlegra karoo</i> Wesolowska, 2006	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Psenuc dependens</i> (Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Thyene inflata</i> (Gerstäcker, 1873)	1	LC	AE
<i>Thyene thyenioides</i> (Lessert, 1925)	1	LC	AE	
Scytodidae	<i>Scytodes arenacea</i> Purcell, 1904	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Scytodes broomi</i> Pocock, 1902	4	DD	SAE
Segestriidae	<i>Ariadna karrooica</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE
Selenopidae	<i>Anyphops barnardi</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	2	LC	STHE
Sicariidae	<i>Hexophthalma hahni</i> (Karsch, 1878) (Fig. 24)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Loxosceles spinulosa</i> Purcell, 1904	4	LC	SAE
Sparassidae	<i>Arandisa deserticola</i> Lawrence, 1938 (Fig. 25)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Eusparassus schoemanae</i> Moradmand, 2013 (Fig. 26)	2	LC	STHE
Theraphosidae	<i>Idiothele nigrofulva</i> (Pocock, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
Theridiidae	<i>Enoplognatha inornata</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Enoplognatha molesta</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Euryopis episinoides</i> (Walckenaer, 1847)	0	LC	C
	<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	0	LC	C
	<i>Latrodectus renivulvatus</i> Dahl, 1902	1	LC	AE

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
PHILODROMIDAE	<i>Hirriusa arenacea</i> (Lawrence, 1927)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Philodromus browningi</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Suemus punctatus</i> Lawrence, 1938	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Thanatus vulgaris</i> Simon, 1870	0	LC	C
	<i>Tibellus minor</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
PHOLCIDAE	<i>Quamtana</i> sp. immature		NE	
	<i>Smeringopus koppies</i> Huber, 2012	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Smeringopus lotzi</i> Hubert, 2012	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Smeringopus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1947	2	LC	STHE
PHYXELIDIDAE	<i>Vidole sothoana</i> Griswold, 1990	2	LC	STHE
PISAURIDAE	<i>Cispus kimbius</i> Blandin, 1978	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
PRODIDOMIDAE	<i>Austrodomus scaber</i> (Purcell, 1904)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Theuma foveolata</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Theuma maculata</i> Purcell, 1907	2	LC	STHE
SALTICIDAE	<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE
	<i>Evarcha prosimilis</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	1	LC	AE
	<i>Heliophanus charlesi</i> Wesolowska, 2003	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Heliophanus debilis</i> Simon, 1901	1	LC	AE
	<i>Heliophanus nanus</i> Wesolowska, 2003	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Heliophanus pistaciae</i> Wesolowska, 2003	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Heliophanus proszynskii</i> Wesolowska, 2003	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Heliophanus termitophagus</i> Wesolowska & Haddad, 2002	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Icius insolidus</i> (Wesolowska, 1999)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Langona warchalowskii</i> Wesolowska, 2007	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Langona hirsuta</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Menemerus transvaalicus</i> Wesolowska, 1999	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Natta chionogaster</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Pellenes bulawayoensis</i> Wesolowska, 2000	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Pellenes geniculatus</i> (Simon, 1868)	0	LC	C
	<i>Pellenes modicus</i> Wesolowska & Russell-Smith, 2000	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Pellenes tharinae</i> Wesolowska, 2007	3	LC	STHE
	<i>Phlegra karoo</i> Wesolowska, 2006	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Psenec dependens</i> (Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Thyene inflata</i> (Gerstäcker, 1873)	1	LC	AE
<i>Thyene thyenioides</i> (Lessert, 1925)	1	LC	AE	
SCYTODIDAE	<i>Scytodes arenacea</i> Purcell, 1904	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Scytodes broomi</i> Pocock, 1902	4	DD	SAE
SEGESTRIIDAE	<i>Ariadna karrooica</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE
SELENOPIDAE	<i>Anyphops barnardi</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	2	LC	STHE
SICARIIDAE	<i>Hexophthalma hahni</i> (Karsch, 1878)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Loxosceles spinulosa</i> Purcell, 1904	4	LC	SAE
SPARASSIDAE	<i>Arandisa deserticola</i> Lawrence, 1938	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Eusparassus schoemanae</i> Moradmand, 2013	2	LC	STHE
THERAPHOSIDAE	<i>Idiothele nigrofulva</i> (Pocock, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
THERIDIIDAE	<i>Enoplognatha inornata</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Enoplognatha molesta</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Euryopsis episinoides</i> (Walckenaer, 1847)	0	LC	C
	<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	0	LC	C
	<i>Latrodectus renivulvatus</i> Dahl, 1902	1	LC	AE

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
THOMISIDAE	<i>Phoroncidia eburnea</i> (Simon, 1895)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Heriaeus allenjonesi</i> Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2013	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE
	<i>Monaeses paradoxus</i> Lucas, 1864	0	LC	C
	<i>Ozyptila caenosa</i> Jézéquel, 1966	1	LC	AE
	<i>Pherecydes tuberculatus</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1883 (Fig. 27)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Simorcus lotzi</i> Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2010	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Stiphropus affinis</i> Lessert, 1923 (Fig. 29)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Thomisus kalaharinus</i> Lawrence, 1936	1	LC	AE
TRACHELIDAE	<i>Thomisus stenningi</i> Pocock, 1900 (Fig. 28)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Afroceto africana</i> (Simon 1910)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Fuchibotulus kigelia</i> Haddad & Lyle, 2008	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Orthobula arca</i> Haddad, Jin & Platnick, 2022 (Fig. 30)	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Poachelas striatus</i> Haddad & Lyle, 2008	3	LC	SAE
ZODARIIDAE	<i>Cydrela friedlanderae</i> Hewitt, 1914	5	DD	SAE
	<i>Cydrela spinifrons</i> Hewitt, 1915	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Cyrioctea lotzi</i> Jocqué, 2013	5	DD	SAE
	<i>Diores poweri</i> Tucker, 1920 (Fig. 31)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Diores triangulifer</i> Simon, 1910	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Heradida loricata</i> Simon, 1893 (Fig. 32)	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Ranops caprivi</i> Jocqué, 1991	2	LC	STHE